

Call: NFRP-2019-2020
Topic: Innovation for Generation II and III reactors

Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

Deliverable D6.7

Report on FRACTESUS training and education activities

Grant Agreement No: 900014
Contractual delivery date: Month 48
Actual delivery date: Month 48
Lead beneficiary: P15 – UC

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2020-2024 under grant agreement No 900014.

Grant Agreement No.	900014
Project full title	Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens (FRACTESUS)
Deliverable number	D6.7
Deliverable title	Report on FRACTESUS training and education activities
Nature¹:	R
Dissemination level²:	PU
Work package number:	WP6
Work package leader:	Sergio Cicero
Author(s):	Marcos Sánchez, Sergio Cicero
Keywords:	Dissemination, social network

The research leading to these results has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2020-2024 under grant agreement No 900014.

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¹ **Nature:** R -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** **PU** -Public; **CO** -Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

D.6.7 – Report on FRACTESUS training and education activities

Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	4
2	FRACTESUS final training seminar	4
3	FRACTESUS Special Sessions.....	8
4	Education.....	10
5	Conclusions.....	10

1 Introduction

An important task developed in the project is to provide training and education to both the scientific community and the industry, and to create European expert knowledge in fracture mechanics testing using sub-sized specimens. This has been achieved through the following activities:

1. Organization of a final training seminar, focused on fracture testing of sub-sized specimens. The event reviews the basics about testing of sub-sized specimens, together with the main issues on the subject, and the knowledge and the progresses generated during the project.
2. Organization of special sessions in relevant international conferences, focused on the issues arising when using sub-sized specimens in fracture testing. These sessions are open to contributions from other projects or institutions working in the field. The main aims are sharing knowledge, finding synergies and exploring new research opportunities, among others.
3. To promote both the international mobility and the generation of expert knowledge in fracture testing using sub-sized specimens. Mobility of researchers and laboratory visits are encouraged within the project partners in order to share knowledge and good practices. Moreover, several young scientist/engineer are complete a PhD programme within FRACTESUS framework.

2 FRACTESUS final training seminar

The FRACTESUS final Seminar took place on September 10 and 11, 2024, in Santander, as shown in the brochure captured in Figure 1. Figure 2 shows different moments of the lectures. This training seminar, whose programme is outlined in Table 1, focused on disseminating the knowledge generated regarding mini-C(T) testing procedures and guidelines, along with highlighting the principal results of the project. The seminar garnered significant interest within both the scientific and industrial communities, attracting 73 attendees (63 in person, 10 on-line) from 15 countries (including USA and Japan, see Table 2) and achieving a successful reception.

The seminar material is available at Open Aire (Open Access), and can be openly downloaded at <https://zenodo.org/records/13785578>.

After the seminar, a brief survey was shared among the attendees. 26 responses were gathered, the main results being gathered in Table 3 and showing a high grade of approval among the participants, being the lowest score 4.19 out of 5.0, with the overall experience being scored with 4.62 (out of 5.0).

September 10-11th 2024

VENUE

September 10-11th 2024

Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2014-2018 under grant agreement N^o 900014

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Suggested accommodation

<p>Hotel Silken Coliseum Plaza Remedios, 1 Phone: +34 942 318 081 silken@hoteles-silken.com Walking distance: 5 min</p>	<p>Hotel Bahía Calle Cádiz, 22 Phone: +34 942 205 000 hotelbahia@sardinerooteles.com Walking distance: 7 min</p>
<p>Hotel Vincci Puertochico Calle Castelar, 25 Phone: +34 942 225 200 puertochico@vinccioteles.com Walking distance: 15 min</p>	<p>Soho Palacio de Pombo Marcelino Sanz de Sautuola, 2 Phone: +34 842 840 804 sbpalaciopombo@sohohoteles.com Walking distance: 5 min</p>

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This seminar is an initiative of the FRACTESUS project (EURATOM grant agreement N^o 900014). It will provide a complete detailed overview of the results of the FRACTESUS project experimental program and the resulting mini-C(T) guidelines and procedures.

Audience
PhD students; professional engineers and researchers working in the fields of fracture mechanics, material characterisation or structural integrity; highly experienced researchers and engineers wishing to update their knowledge and share experiences.

Fee
There is no fee, but registration is mandatory by sending an email to the organizers, specifying:

- Name:
- Family name:
- Organization:

Figure 1. FRACTESUS seminar flyer (1st page).

Figure 2. Different moments during FRACTESUS seminar.

Table 1. FRACTESUS seminar final programme.

Day 1		
Time	Title	Lecturer
9:00-9:30	Welcome and registration	
<i>Chair: Inge Uytdenhouwen, SCK CEN</i>		
9:30-10:00	FRACTESUS project: an overview	Giovanni Bonny, SCK CEN
10:00-10:45	The Master Curve methodology	Pentti Arffman, VTT
10:45-11:15	Coffee Break & Networking	
<i>Chair: Mark Kirk, PEAI</i>		
11:15-12:00	Recent revisions of foreign MC standards (E1921 and JEAC4216)	Masato Yamamoto, CRIEPI
12:00-12:45	Mini-C(T) specimens: overview and their use for Master Curve characterisation	I.Uytdenhouwen,SCK CEN
12:45-13:30	FRACTESUS round robin on non-irradiated materials	Eberhard Altstadt, HZDR
13:30-14:30	Lunch	
<i>Chair: Giovanni Bonny, SCK CEN</i>		
14:30-15:15	FRACTESUS round robin on irradiated materials	Radim Kopriva, UJV
15:15-16:00	Fractographic examination of mini-C(T) specimens	Susan Ortner, UKNNL
16:00-16:45	Mini-C(T) modeling: main findings	Pierrick Francois, CEA
16:45-17:30	FRACTESUS Guidelines	Florian Obermeier, Framatome
17:30-17:45	Questions and seminar adjourn for the day	
Day 2		
Time	Title	Lecturer
<i>Chair: Marta Serrano, CIEMAT</i>		
09:00-09:30	Constraint analysis on mini-C(T) specimens	Philippe Spätig, PSI
09:30-10:00	Mini-C(T) application on structural steels	Marcos Sánchez, UC
10:00-10:45	International perspectives on mini-C(T) testing: USA	Mark Kirk, PEAI
10:45-11:15	Coffee Break	
<i>Chair: Masato Yamamoto, CRIEPI</i>		
11:15-12:00	International perspectives on mini-C(T) testing: Japan	Tomoki Shinko, CRIEPI
12:00-13:30	European projects for LTO of NPPs: KLEINPROBEN INCEFA SCALE STRUMAT LTO ENTENTE	Eberhard Altstadt, HZDR Sergio Arrieta, UC Murthy Kolluri, NRG Marta Serrano, CIEMAT
13:30-13:45	Seminar Closure	

Table 2. FRACTESUS seminar list of attendants.

Name	Company	Name	Company
Alejandro Palacio	ENSA, Spain	Mark Kirk	Phoenix Engineering Associates, Inc., USA
Audrey Somera	IRSN, France	Marta Horvath	HUN-REN-CER, Hungary
Aurore Parrot	EDF R&D, France	Marta Serrano	CIEMAT, Spain
Benoit Tanguy	CEA Saclay, France	Masato Yamamoto	CRIEPI, Japan
Bonny Giovanni	SCK CEN, Belgium	Mikhail Sokolov	Oak Ridge National Laboratory, USA
Borja Arroyo	Universidad de Cantabria, Spain	Murthy Kolluri	NRG, The Netherlands
Carolyn Fairbanks	US Nuclear Regulatory Commission, USA	Mykola Dzubinsky	European Commission, Belgium
Csaba Takács	BZN, Hungary	Naiara Bravo	Azterlan, Spain
David Solana	ENSA, Spain	Nick Riddle	Rolls-Royce, UK
Diego Ferreño	Universidad de Cantabria, Spain	Pål Efsing	Vattenfall, Sweden
Diego Mora	PSI, Switzerland	Pentti Arffman	VTT, Finland
Eberhard Altstadt	HZDR, Germany	Petr Gal	UJV Rez, Czech Republic
Elliot Long	EPRI, USA	Philippe Spätig	PSI, Switzerland
Enrique Gómez	ENSA, Spain	Pierre-Guy Vincent	IRSN, France
Ermile Gaganidze	KIT, Germany	Pierrick François	CEA Saclay, France
Federico Gutiérrez-Solana	Universidad de Cantabria, Spain	Radim Kopriva	UJV Rez, Czech Republic
Ferenc Gillemot	HUN-REN-CER, Hungary	Ralph Doering	ENSI, Switzerland
Florian Obermeier	Framatome, Germany	Raúl Muñoz	ENSA, Spain
Frederic Perales	IRSN, France	Sarah Saanouni	CEA Saclay, France
Gintautas Dundulis	KTU, Lithuania	Sergio Arrieta	Universidad de Cantabria, Spain
Grace Burke	University of Manchester, UK	Sergio Cicero	Universidad de Cantabria, Spain
Haruko Sasaki	Japan Nuclear Regulation Authority, Japan	Sreeram T. Madabusi	UK Atomic Energy Authority, UK
Helen Swan	National Nuclear Laboratory, UK	Susan Ortner	National Nuclear Laboratory, UK
Ibon Miguel	Azterlan, Spain	Szabolcs Szávai	BZN, Hungary
Ildikó Szenthe	HUN-REN-CER, Hungary	Timo Metzler	KIT, Germany
Inge Uytendhouwen	SCK CEN, Belgium	Tohru Tobita	Japan Atomic Energy Agency, Japan
Isaac Rivas Pelayo	Universidad de Cantabria, Spain	Tomohiro Hojo	Japan Nuclear Regulation Authority, Japan
Ivan Kurt Ohm	ENSA, Spain	Tomoki Shinko	CRIEPI, Japan
Ivana Schnablova	UJV Rez, Czech Republic	Verónica Román	ENSA, Spain
Jean Smith	EPRI, USA	Víctor Calzada Cabano	Universidad de Cantabria, Spain
Johan Blomström	Ringhals AB – Vattenfall, Sweden	Virginia Madrazo	ENSA, Spain
Jorge Elices	ENSA, Spain	Vladimir Slugen	STUBA, Slovakia
Jose Adolfo Sainz-Aja	Universidad de Cantabria, Spain	Zoltán Bézi	BZN, Hungary
Jose Alberto Alvarez	Universidad de Cantabria, Spain		
Judit Dudra	BZN, Hungary		
Justin Yarrington	Idaho National Laboratory / Battelle Energy Alliance, USA		
Luis Espinoza	Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain		
Marcos Sánchez	Tecnalia, Spain		
Mariana Rodrigues	SCK CEN, Belgium		
Marjorie Erickson	Phoenix Engineering Associates, Inc., USA		

Table 3. Results of the Seminar survey

Question	Average grade		Rate		
	Grade	Count	Very bad	Good	Excellent
Rate your overall experience of the seminar	4.62	1	Very bad	5	Excellent
Was the structure of the seminar appropriated?	4.62	1	Poor	5	Excellent
Were the topics covered relevant to fracture mechanics and mini-CT testing?	4.76	1	Not at all	5	Extremely relevant
Was the information provided at the right level?	4.54	1	Poor	5	Excellent
How would you rate the quality of the speakers?	4.62	1	Very bad	5	Excellent
Were the speakers dynamic and engaging?	4.19	1	Not at all	5	Extremely engaging
Were the seminar contents useful for your training?	4.42	1	Not at all	5	Extremely useful
Were the presentations informative?	4.58	1	Not at all	5	Extremely interesting
How would you rate the organization and logistics of the seminar?	4.69	1	Very bad	5	Excellent
How would you rate the venue and facilities?	4.20	1	Very bad	5	Excellent
Was the length of the seminar appropriate?	4.42	1	Too short	5	Too long

3 FRACTESUS Special Sessions

During the ASME PVP 2023 Pressure Vessels and Piping Conference held in Atlanta, USA, in July 2023, two special sessions were dedicated to the project. Seven contributions were presented, with their respective paper proceedings published in the ASME digital collection (<https://asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/>). These successful events made it possible to complete the deliverables D6.4 by month 30 and D6.6, which was expected by month 48, along with the achievement of milestones MS17 and MS20. Besides, the second special session was shared with contributions of the sister H2020 project, STRUMAT-LTO.

Additionally, a third special session was organized during the ASME PVP 2024 Pressure Vessels and Piping Conference in Bellevue, USA, in July 2024. In this session, four contributions were presented, with each one being accompanied by their corresponding paper published in the ASME digital collections. One additional FRACTESUS presentation was completed in a separate session dedicated to European projects (e.g., STRUMAT-LTO), revealing the potential and synergies between them.

Summary of the contributions:

- First special session:
 1. G. Bonny, E. Altstadt, P. Arffman, S. Cicero, F. Obermeier, T. Petit, H. Swan, R. Chaouadi, E. Gaganidze, B. Hargitai, M. Kolluri, R. Kopriva, P. Rozsahegyi, M. Serrano, P. Spätig, I. Uytendhouwen, H. Wilcox, M. Yamamoto, Present Status of the Fractesus Project: Round Robin on Unirradiated Materials, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-105449>.
 2. A. Das, P. Chekhonin, M. Houska, F. Obermeier, E. Altstadt, Fractography of Neutron Irradiated RPV Steels – A Comparison of Shift in Reference Temperature and Net Hardening, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-103648>.
 3. F. Naziris, R. Hernandez Pascual, T. Metzler, E. Gaganidze, I. Uytendhouwen, M. Kolluri, Master Curve Evaluation Using Miniature C(T) Specimens as Part of a Round Robin Program Within the FRACTESUS Project, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-107254>.
 4. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, Fracture Characterization of Structural Steel S275JR Using Conventional CT Specimens, Mini-CT Specimens and Small Punch Specimens: A Comparison, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-105437>.
- Second special session:
 1. Metzler, E. Gaganidze, J. Aktaa, Numerical Prediction of Fracture Toughness of a Reactor Pressure Vessel Steel Based on Experiments Using Small Specimens, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-105918>.
 2. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, S. Arrieta, Literature Review on Testing of Mini-CT Specimen to Characterize the Ductile-to-Brittle Transition Range and the Upper Shelf Regime, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-105596>.
 3. M. Li, R. Chaouadi, I. Uytendhouwen, T. Pardoën, G. Bonny, The Effect of Loss of Constraint on the Initiation of Ductile Fracture in a Mini-CT, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2023-106216>.
- Third special session:
 1. G. Bonny, I. Uytendhouwen, E. Altstadt, P. Arffman, S. Cicero, F. Obermeier, T. Petit, P. François, B. Tanguy, H. Swan, H. Wilcox, Present Status of the Fractesus Project: Numerical and Experimental Round Robins on Irradiated and Unirradiated

Materials. Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).

2. F. Obermeier, I. Uytendhouwen, E. Altstadt, S. Cicero, M. Sánchez, J. Echols, G. Bonny, Fractesus Project: Fracture Toughness Round Robin on a High Copper Weld Using Miniature C(T) Specimens – Results and Discussion, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).
3. S. Ortner, M. Sánchez, J. Echols, S. Cicero, P. Chekhonin, Validity of Toughness Measurements From Miniature Specimens Failing in Different Fracture Modes, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).
4. A. Somera, F. Perales, P-G. Vincent, Fracture Toughness Tests on Western RPV Steels Using Small Scale Specimen Technique – Evaluation of Results, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).

The mentioned additional presentation in separate session of ASME PVP2024 is:

5. M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, F. Obermaier, M. Serrano, Y-L. Chiu, E. Altstadt, On the possibility of extending the crack length criterion in the master curve methodology, Volume 1: Codes & Standards, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (2024).

4 Education

Several PhD students were actively engaged in FRACTESUS activities. Three PhD Thesis were successfully completed:

- Dr. Li Meng completed his Thesis at SCK-CEN in 2023 on “Specimen miniaturization for fracture toughness determination of reactor pressure vessel steels – an experimental and modeling investigation”. Supervised by Prof. Thomas Pardoen, Prof. Ludovic Noels (UC Louvain) and Dr. Inge Uytendhouwen (SCK-CEN).
- Dr. Marcos Sánchez completed his Thesis at UC in 2024 on “Fracture characterization on Structural Steels by means of mini-C(T) specimens”. Supervised by Prof. Sergio Cicero and Dr. Borja Arroyo (UC).
- Dr. Timo Metzler completed his Thesis at KIT in 2024 on “Numerical Prediction of Fracture Toughness of a Reactor Pressure Vessel Steel Based on Experiments Using Small Specimens”. Supervised by Ermile Gaganidze, Jarir Aktaa (KIT).

Moreover, during the period of 2021-2022, one PhD student and one MSc student participated in FRACTESUS activities at Bay Zoltán Foundation.

5 Conclusions

With all these activities, the project success in the proposals established at the beginning of the project and fulfills the EC commitments.

